

THERMAL INSULATION MATERIALS: BENEFITS AND PRODUCTION

Islomov Aliakbar

Lecturer of Samarkand State Architectural and Civil Engineering Institute

Abstract: The thermal insulation materials presented on the modern market are striking in their diversity, among which it is not easy to make the right choice. Within the framework of this article, we will determine what characteristics should be paid attention to, what advantages and disadvantages certain types of materials have and what they are made of.

Keywords: thermal insulation, raw materials, energy saving, water absorption, heat capacity

Introduction

The main function of the thermal insulation material is to prevent heat loss from the insulated room, for example, during the cold season, and heat penetration inside - in hot summer. Heat transfer is due to the movement of molecules, which cannot be completely stopped, but can be reduced. So, in still dry air, the molecules move the slowest. It is this property that was taken as the basis for the production of heat-insulating materials, which are air packed in various ways: in pores, cells, capsules.

Materials

When choosing one or another insulating material, you should pay attention to several fundamental characteristics.

The coefficient of thermal conductivity is the main indicator for thermal insulation materials. It shows the amount of heat that passes through a material having a thickness of 1 m and an area of 1 m² in one hour, provided that the temperature difference on opposite surfaces is 10 ° C. For example, the coefficient of thermal conductivity of dry air is 0.023 W / (m * C). The value of thermal

conductivity is affected by other characteristics of the material: porosity, humidity, temperature, chemical composition, and others.

Porosity - the percentage of air pores in the total volume of the product. It can be 50% or more. In some cellular plastics, it reaches 90 - 98%. Pores can be open, closed, small or large. Their uniform distribution within the material is very important.

Humidity is the amount of moisture contained in a material. This parameter affects the thermal conductivity. Since water conducts heat very well, a material saturated with water - wet, will not perform its functions.

Water absorption - the ability of a material to absorb water in direct contact with it. A very important point for external insulation, which may be under precipitation, for internal insulation in rooms with a high level of humidity. If the material absorbs water, its properties will drop.

Vapor permeability - the amount of water vapor passing through a material with a thickness of 1 m and an area of 1 m², in 1 hour, provided that the temperature is the same on both sides of the material, and the difference in partial vapor pressure is 1 Pa. This parameter affects the need for arranging additional vapor barrier.

The density of a material affects its mass. It can be used to calculate how heavy the structure will be if one or another material of a certain thickness is used.

Biostability determines whether fungi, mold and other pathogenic flora can develop on the surface or inside the structure of the material.

The heat capacity of a material is important in regions with frequent temperature changes. It shows the amount of heat that the insulation can store.

There are other characteristics: fire resistance, strength, frost resistance, bending strength and fire safety indicators. When choosing a material, you should also pay attention to them, as well as to another indicator that is not directly related to a specific heat-insulating material:

Coefficient U - the ability of the structure to transmit heat. Whether it is walls, ceiling or floor, depending on the materials from which they are made, they can pass heat in different amounts and at different speeds. This coefficient is a combined

value, the calculation of which includes all the materials used in layers and the air gaps between them. The value of the U-value of a particular building or structure will determine which thermal insulation material can be used and what thickness of this material is required.

Results

To date, the production of thermal insulation materials has been established, both from inorganic and organic raw materials. Let's consider them separately because of their different impact on the environment and humans, as well as the conditions of disposal.

Mineral wool is perhaps the most common material at the moment. It is produced from mineral raw materials: dolomites, basalts and other minerals. The fibers obtained as a result of the melting of minerals are held together by a binder, which is often a phenol-formaldehyde resin. The ease of production has led to a low price for this material.

Benefits of mineral wool:

Good thermal insulation properties.

Practically does not absorb moisture.

Frost-resistant.

Can serve as additional sound insulation.

Does not burn.

Durable.

Does not change its characteristics.

Not subject to decay.

"Breathing".

Disadvantages:

Not strong enough.

Requires vapor barrier.

Requires waterproofing.

Phenol formaldehyde is a toxic substance.

Requires special disposal.

Release form: loose cotton wool, mats, cylinders, plates with different densities (light, soft, semi-rigid, rigid).

Stone wool is made from diabase rock by melting and converting the liquid mass into fibers. Such material is 99% air and only 1% rock. It is used for insulation of walls and other structures everywhere.

Benefits of stone wool:

Provides soundproofing.

Does not burn.

Not subject to decay.

Prevents the spread of fire. Melts at 1000°C.

Disadvantages:

Energy intensive production process.

Requires special disposal.

Foam glass (cellular glass) is made from glass powder by sintering it with blowing agents. Air occupies 80 - 95% of the material.

Advantages of foam glass:

Durable. You can drive nails.

Waterproof.

Frost-resistant.

Does not burn.

Not subject to decay.

Durable.

Disadvantages:

Does not "breathe" (additional ventilation is required).

Expensive.

Perlite is a volcanic rock. When heated, it increases several times, which is why the production process resembles the creation of popcorn. It has been used for thermal insulation since the middle of the last century.

Perlite Benefits:

Environmentally friendly material.

Does not burn.

Does not absorb moisture.

Doesn't settle.

Resistant to decay and the influence of pathogenic flora

Easy to use (you can fall asleep or blow into voids).

Recycled by composting (improves soil quality).

Disadvantages:

It can spill out of voids during the laying of pipes or cables in the walls.

Heat-insulating materials from inorganic raw materials also include various heat-insulating concretes: aerated concrete, cellular concrete, foam concrete. As well as concrete with aggregates: expanded clay concrete, perlite concrete, polystyrene concrete.

Extruded polystyrene foam has a solid, durable microstructure. The cells are closed, impermeable and filled with air. Neither water nor air can penetrate from cell to cell.

Advantages of extruded polystyrene foam:

Good thermal conductivity.

Inert to most substances.

Does not absorb moisture.

Stronger than foam.

Disadvantages:

Flammable (in the process of combustion it releases toxic substances).

Doesn't "breathe".

Polystyrene foams are small balls fastened together. They can be produced both by pressing and non-pressing methods.

Advantages of polystyrene foams:

Inexpensive.

Durable.

Well insulated.

Convenient to install.

Disadvantages:

Under the influence of sunlight turn yellow and disintegrate.

They don't "breathe".

They are burning.

When moisture penetrates, the structure is destroyed.

Polyurethane foam is a liquid heat-insulating material. When the ingredients are mixed with air, a finely dispersed aerosol is formed, which can be sprayed onto a surface with any geometry.

Advantages of polyurethane foam:

Amazing elasticity of the material.

Resistant to fungus and mold.

You can insulate uneven surfaces.

Easy installation that does not take much time.

Has no joints.

Disadvantages:

It burns, releasing toxic substances.

Doesn't "breathe".

Installation requires a special installation.

Paper has been used for insulation since the middle of the last century. Such materials are granules obtained from newspapers and other waste paper. To blow these pellets into the voids in the walls, the help of specialists is needed.

Advantages of paper-based thermal insulation materials:

Do not burn (treated with neutral salts).

Repel water.

Fills cavities well.

Easy to use.

Do not harm the environment.

Dispose of by conventional composting.

Resistant to fungus.

No additional vapor barrier required.

Disadvantages:

Limited scope due to the specific shape of the product - granules.

Flax is used as a heater quite rarely, mainly by those who care about the environment and their health. The reason for the non-ubiquitous distribution of linen materials is the high price. Although it is expected to decline over time.

Advantages of linen insulation:

Excellent insulating qualities.

No additional vapor barrier required.

Dispose of by incineration or composting.

Absolutely natural.

Resistant to fungi and microorganisms.

Disadvantages:

Difficult to cut.

Additional fire protection required.

Wood fiber (cellulose wadding) is currently considered one of the best known organic thermal insulation materials. It is a wood material, crushed to the state of cotton wool. It is produced both in loose form and in slabs. It is used for blowing into the cavity of the walls.

Advantages of cellulose wool:

Increased thermal insulation properties.

Serves as soundproofing.

Simple and easy to use.

Compostable.

Disadvantages:

Subject to decay and fungus.

Cannot be used to insulate hollow walls in old buildings.

Ammonium polyphosphate has been added to improve the refractory qualities.

Discussion

Before choosing a material for insulation, it is advisable to consult with specialists. Based on the material of the walls, their thickness and operating

conditions (climate), they will advise which materials can be suitable in a particular case and what should be their thickness. If you did not hear the material that you would like to use in the list of proposed options, specify this nuance. Perhaps this material simply fell out of the attention of a specialist, or maybe it is categorically not suitable for this design.

Conclusion

In the construction of modern high-rise buildings, foam plastic and other polymeric materials are widely used, since their price is low, they are easy to install and have good thermal conductivity. But basically no one thinks about the impact of such materials on human life. For developers, it is enough that the manufacturer assured of the safety of the product.

Literature

1. Rizaev, I. (2021). Liberalization of the social system: constructive and destructive aspects. *TRANS Asian Journal of Marketing & Management Research*, 10(4), 58-64.
2. Rizaev, I. I. (2019). The structure of the social system as the basis for the self-organization of society. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 1(7), 190-195.
3. Imomalievich, R. I. (2020). Synergetic interpretation of society development. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development*, 5(3), 5-5.
4. Сафаров, А. И., &Ризаев, И. И. (2021). Этапы самоорганизации социальной системы. In *В поисках социальной истины* (pp. 237-242).
5. Сафаров, А. И., &Ризаев, И. И. (2021). Возможности и перспективы экотуризма в Узбекистане. In *Экономика и управление госте приимством территории* (pp. 123-127).
6. Ризаев, И. И., &Муминова, З. О. (2021). Профессиональная подготовка личности: оздоровление и духовное воспитание. In *Система менеджмента качества в вузе: здоровье, образованность, конкурентно способность*(pp. 264-268).

7. Rizaev, I. I. (2019). Evolutionary mechanisms of self-organization of the social system. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University, 1(9), 81-86.
8. Аликулов, С., &Ризаев, И. И. (2021). Образование и современныетехнологии. In Моделирование и конструирование в образовательнойсреде (pp. 27-31).
9. Ризаев, И. И. (2021). Проблемы либерализации общества в контексте глобализации. Онтологические и социокультурные основания альтернативного проекта глобализации.—Екатеринбург, 2021, 254-257.
10. Ризаев, И. И. (2020). Методологические аспекты исследования социальных систем. Общество в контексте социокультурных трансформаций. Биробиджан ПГУ им. Шолом-Алейхема, 92-98.
11. Ризаев, И. И. (2019). Механизмы самоорганизации социальных систем. Экономика и социум, (3), 368-371.
12. Alikulov, S. A., &Rizaev, I. I. (2020). Methodological problems of research of social systems. Theoretical & Applied Science, (2), 717-720.
13. Ризаев, И. И. (2020). Методологические аспекты исследования социальных систем. Общество в контексте социокультурных трансформаций. Биробиджан ПГУ им. Шолом-Алейхема, 92-98.
14. Ҳаққулов Н. Қ. Сиддиқий-Ажзий маърифатпарварлик қарашларида миллий толерантлик масаласи //НамДУ илмий ахборотномаси-Научный вестник НамГУ. – 2020. – №. 10. – С. 296.
15. Сафаров А. И., Ҳаққулов Н. К. Свойственные качества совершенному человеку в суфизме //Современная наука как социально-политический фактор развития государства. – 2019. – С. 48-50.
16. Ҳаққулов Н. Қ. Сиддиқий-Ажзийнинг ижтимоий-фалсафий қарашлари. – 2020.
17. Naqqulov N. Q. International tolerance in the educational views of Siddiki-Ajzi //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2020. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 262-268.